

Probabilistic surface change detection with a 2-d array of robust adaptive Kalman filters

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Abstract—The ability to collect high spatial and temporal resolution topographic data has increased interest in analyzing topographic changes resulting from dynamic surface processes. However comparing surveys directly compounds error and uncertainty from each source, prompting efforts to account for observation noise and other sources of uncertainty. The Kalman filter provides a solution to spatio-temporal modelling that has historically suffered from several challenges, notably the reliance on the accurate parameterization of noise statistics. This research presents the use of a 2-d array of robust adaptive Kalman filters to demonstrate the use of state-space models for probabilistic change detection. Four LiDAR surveys of a small basin affected by the 2018 Eastern Iburi landslide in Hokkaido, Japan were collected between October 2021 and June 2022. Rates of vertical displacement experienced by a bare-soil hillslope and were documented by the subtraction of survey DEMs and by estimation with the Kalman array. The spatial distributions of the probabilities associated with these estimates, along with model performance and uncertainty were shown to be useful tools for investigating surface change.

I. INTRODUCTION

Low-cost surveying technology such as multi-sensor remotely piloted aerial systems (RPAS), have provided a platform for the collection of high spatial and temporal resolution topographic data. Data collected from RPAS mounted radar, photographic, or light detection and ranging (LiDAR) sensors are readily processed into digital elevation models (DEMs) [1]. While the specifications of the resulting elevation models are largely mission specific [2], vertical and horizontal accuracy of 1–20 cm and spatial resolutions of 5–50 cm are common [3,4]. These properties have made RPAS-derived topographic data ideal for monitoring dynamic systems such as natural hazards [5].

Multiple topographic surveys can form a spatio-temporal time-series of elevation observations from which many dynamic geomorphological phenomena can be examined. A common practice to introduce the temporal dimension to the data is to subtract elevation models, creating difference of DEMs (DoDs). These data quantify vertical displacement on a cell-by-cell basis, and are often used to derive volumetric change when investigating various dynamic processes [6]. However, comparing multiple DEMs propagates error and uncertainty from both sources into the results [7].

Probabilistic thresholding has been widely used to minimize erroneous elevation differences by restricting the analysis to high confidence estimates [7]. This is generally accomplished by estimating a local uncertainty field and deriving an associated probability using a statistical distribution. However, these analyses are highly dependent on the non-trivial task of accurately estimating local uncertainty [8]. Despite this challenge, accounting for noise when comparing multi-temporal elevation observations has proven to be a valuable endeavor for surface change detection and analysis [7,8].

Kalman filters are optimal estimators when noise statistics are known and Gaussian [9], and are widely employed to model discrete-time dynamic systems. The primary advantage offered by Kalman filters is the ability to account for multiple sources of noise and provide an internal estimate of uncertainty. However, filter performance is highly dependent on noise statistic parameters, resulting in the development of robust adaptive Kalman filters. This research will demonstrate the use of these filters to provide estimates of vertical displacement rates and the probability that the estimated vertical displacement rates are not zero given the uncertainty in each system.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The theory and governing equations of Kalman filters are well-documented, and will not be reiterated in the interest of brevity. The equations behind the robust adaptive Kalman filter can be found in [10]. Robust adaptive Kalman filters differ from conventional Kalman filters by inflating uncertainty based on the accuracy of the model state relative to a robust estimate using current observations. The state vector (x) is defined by the coefficients of bivariate polynomial (β_1) concatenated with a companion vector representing the average rate of change for the polynomial coefficients (β_2). The state extrapolation matrix (A) follows a first-order kinematic model which extrapolates the rate of change vector over the time difference between surveys (Δ_t) to predict the next polynomial coefficients.

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad A = \begin{bmatrix} I & I\Delta_t \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix}, \quad x_{t+1} = A_t x_t$$

where I is an identity matrix with dimensions equal to the number of coefficients in the polynomial.

The observation vector (y) is a vectorized local window of elevation observations (z) taken at a position and time.

$$y_{r,c} = \begin{bmatrix} z_0 \\ \vdots \\ z_n \end{bmatrix} = \text{vec} \left(\begin{bmatrix} z_{r-w,c-w} & \cdots & z_{r-w,c+w} \\ \vdots & z_{r,c} & \vdots \\ z_{r+w,c-w} & \cdots & z_{r+w,c+w} \end{bmatrix} \right)$$

where r and c are row and column indices for a location and w is the half-length of the local window.

The observation model (C) projects the state into observation space as a vector of estimated elevation values (\bar{y}). The observation model is obtained by performing the basis expansion on the spatial positions of each observation (Φ) in the local window. Φ and C by extension are matrices of local spatial position monomials suitable for the task of estimating polynomial coefficients with least squares regression on y .

$$C = [\Phi \ 0], \quad \bar{y}_t = Cx_t$$

Finally, the process uncertainty matrix (Q) is set to zero, assuming no process uncertainty in the state error. Instead, state error uncertainty is captured entirely by robust adaptive uncertainty inflation.

III. METHODS

A. Study site

The study area is a small basin that drains into the Atsuma River and the reservoir formed by the Apporo Dam in Hokkaido, Japan (Fig. 1A). The area experienced many severe co-seismic landslides resulting from the 2018 Eastern Iburu earthquake. The study site focusses on a small, bare-soil hillslope with an area of approximately 0.024 km^2 . The surface features relatively thick (1–3 m) and impermeable tephra layers from Shikotsu caldera

volcanoes (9–20 ka), underlain by partially exposed Neogene sedimentary rocks. As a result, erosion and deposition processes dominate the surface dynamics of this area following the initial disturbance caused by the landslide.

Figure 1. An air photograph and DoDs of the study site draped over the corresponding hillshade images. Subfigure A shows a photograph collected during the 2021-10-13 survey, and subfigures B–D show the difference in elevation, expressed as a rate (m/day) between the date and the previous date for 2021-10-29, 2022-04-25, and 2021-06-28 respectively. The total volume of displaced material is annotated.

B. Data collection

Four surveys were conducted on the following dates: 2021-10-13, 2021-10-29, 2022-04-25, 2022-06-28 (YYYY-MM-DD) using a DJI Matrice 300 RTK RPAS equipped with a DJI Zenmuse L1 LiDAR sensor. While the study area is generally barren, some vegetation regrowth is observable as large positive vertical displacement in the western valley bottom of the 2022-06-28 survey (Fig. 1D), and was confirmed by aerial photography. A DJI D-RTK2 global navigation satellite system (GNSS) receiver was used as the local base station to perform real-time kinematic (RTK) correction of the aircraft positions. Based on this fixed base, a centimeter-level positional accuracy both in horizontal and vertical components was achieved. The LiDAR point clouds were post-processed and filtered using the equipped DJI Terra and ScanX online software (Locus Blue Co., Ltd., <https://scanx.jp/>). Interpolation into DEMs with a spatial resolution of 0.15 m was performed using natural neighbor interpolation in WhiteboxTools. All DEMs were clipped to 1465 rows and 1579 columns, sharing 1,070,251 coincident cells of data.

C. Analysis

A 2-d array of Kalman filters, each based on second-order bivariate polynomials, was initialized for all locations with the following parameter values:

$$P_0 = I \times 0.01, \quad R = I \times 0.01^2, \quad Q = 0$$

where I are identity matrices, P_0 is the initial estimate covariance matrix, referred to as uncertainty hereafter, and R is the measurement uncertainty matrix. The expression for R is based on the estimated measurement root mean squared error (RMSE) of 0.01 m, and is squared to represent a variance. All Kalman filters and the 2-d array were implemented in Python using the scientific computing package NumPy.

Observations were obtained with a local 3×3 window centered on the location of each Kalman filter (i.e., a roving window). The initial state vectors were estimated by weighted least squares (WLS) regression using C , weighted by R , and based on the observations from first and second DEMs available. Subsequent DEMs were processed sequentially using the Kalman filter predict-update functions on local windows of observations.

The normalized estimate error squared (NEES, denoted as ϵ) metric quantifies the squared error of the estimate normalized by the uncertainty covariance matrix. Here, error is defined as the difference between the state estimate and a null hypothesis of zero change (i.e., a zero vector). NEES is a chi-squared distributed variable with degrees of freedom equal to the dimensionality of the vector [11], so the conversion to probability is readily obtained by the chi-squared cumulative distribution function. Only the elements of the estimate uncertainty covariance matrix corresponding to the change coefficients (P_{β_2}) are used.

$$\epsilon = (\beta_2 - 0)^T P_{B_2}^{-1} (\beta_2 - 0)$$

While the entire change vector can be used for probabilistic change detection, inclusive or exclusive of change in position (i.e., polynomial intercept), only the rate of change in vertical position is examined in this research. Model error was evaluated using the RMSE of the posterior state estimate projected into measurement space (\bar{y}) relative to DEM observations.

IV. RESULTS

The spatial distributions of posterior estimate of vertical displacement rate are shown in Fig. 2A1–C1, and can be compared to the corresponding DoDs (Fig. 1). In general, Kalman estimates were smaller and were less impacted by noise (e.g., Fig. 1D and Fig. 2C1). The survey Kalman filters disagreed with the DoD by estimating small, widespread negative vertical displacement with pronounced erosion in the gullies and both deposition and erosion in the valley (Fig. 2A1). The 2022-04-25 and 2022-06-28 Kalman filters maintained this pattern with negative vertical displacement occurring in the gullies and along

the steep hillslope face. The spatial distributions of the non-zero vertical displacement probability (Fig. 2A2–C2) were generally correlated with high vertical displacement; however they also reflected the estimate uncertainty. All dates showed a high probability of vertical displacement in the valley bottom (Fig. 2), which corresponded to deposition areas in Fig. 2A2–C1. Relatively large negative vertical displacements from erosion were observed in the gullies, although the low probabilities suggest that the models had low confidence in these estimates (Fig. 2). Vegetation regrowth was observed as large positive displacement in 2022-06-28 with low probability (Fig. 2C1 and C2). Alternatively, the steep hillslope face experienced consistent negative vertical displacement with relatively high probability.

Figure 2. Kalman estimates of the rate of vertical displacement (m/day) are shown on the left column (subfigures A1, B1, and C1) and the associated probabilities on the right column (subfigures A2, B2, and C2). The total volume of displaced material is annotated.

Large predicted changes may be indicative of poor model performance rather than true change, and low probabilities may be indicative of high uncertainty. The spatial distributions of Kalman filter model RMSE and uncertainty are shown in Fig. 3A and B respectively. Centimeter scale model error was achieved, with the largest errors occurring along the rough, steep section of the hillslope (Fig. 3A). Uncertainty was generally correlated with the gullies, valley, and the upper hillslope (Fig. 3B).

Figure 3. Spatial distributions of elevation error for the predicted 3×3 neighbourhood are shown in subfigures A1–A3. Spatial distributions of uncertainty are expressed as the square root of the posterior estimate error variance and are shown in subfigures B1–B3.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Data from the hidden state may be analyzed with the assumption that uncertainty is minimized if model error is sufficiently low and models are considered reliable. The predicted vertical displacements disagreed with the DoD estimates, favoring erosive processes over depositional processes. The volume of displaced material for the DoD estimates are likely overestimated, especially for 2021-10-29 given the short 16 day time window. In general, the Kalman filters estimated more reasonable displacement volumes with low uncertainty, suggesting that the Kalman filters were more reliable estimators than DoDs. The robust adaptive Kalman filters remained performant without calibrating the initial uncertainty statistics, addressing a key weakness of conventional Kalman filters. The results suggest that the 2-d array of robust adaptive Kalman filters are an improvement over DoDs for analyzing surface dynamics such as vertical displacement while also providing spatially distributed estimates of uncertainty for probabilistic thresholding. The analysis can be readily extended to all change vector coefficients, and polynomial coefficients. Therefore, the Kalman array represents a novel and robust approach to interrogating the spatial relationships of surfaces, including dynamics, along with the associated geomorphological processes.

To the authors' best knowledge, this was the first time state-space modelling has been implemented in an array for multi-temporal local topographic analysis. The presentation of the concept with this simple case study revealed important considerations involving data preprocessing and parameterizing Q . Applying vertical alignment prior to filtering or restricting models to be exact predictors could help represent vertical processes such as erosion and deposition. Q was removed in this research to eliminate potentially erroneous parameterization and limit uncertainty inflation at the risk of creating overconfident models. This may underestimate uncertainty of known processes (e.g., seasonal processes), and may not always be appropriate. Further experimentation is required to identify the optimal strategy for Q estimation over a variety of surface dynamics.

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